

Analysis of Nutritional Components, Crude Fibre and Phytochemical Constituents of Varieties of Different Millets from the Vidarbha Region.

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Abstract- Millets are considered as rich source of energy, carbohydrate and protein as compared to other cereals and have more calcium, iron, zinc, fibre and vitamins content. The presence of high fibre and secondary metabolites in millets help in the prevention of many diseases. Different types of varieties of millets were analyzed for their nutritional properties, fibre content, antioxidant property and phytochemicals. The samples of different varieties of millets were collected from Vidarbha region of Maharashtra. The results showed that highest crude fibre contents are in PKV Kalyani 12.6% in variety of Sorghum followed Finger, Little and Foxtail millet. The study revealed that phytochemicals such as Carbohydrates, Glycosides, Phenols are present in all varieties of millets. Regarding nutritional properties, proteins concentration is highest in CSV45 variety of sorghum whereas Carbohydrates are highest in Dopoli-3 variety of Finger millet and Crude fats are highest in Phule Nachni having 8.2% variety of finger millet. The antioxidant potential estimated by total phenolic content across the millet varieties ranged from 130 µg/ml to 235 µg/ml.

Keywords- Millet, Phytochemicals, Nutritional properties, health benefits, fibres.

I. INTRODUCTION

Millets are regarded as some of the earliest cereals, having been cultivated thousands of years ago at the advent of human civilization. They are valued for their resilience in diverse climatic conditions and their nutritional benefits. Millets are known for being gluten-free and rich in nutrients such as protein, fibre, vitamins, and minerals. These grains play an important role in the diets of many communities around the world, particularly in regions where they are native or have been traditionally cultivated. Additionally, millets are gaining popularity as health-conscious consumers seek out alternative grains with nutritional benefits. It is well known that these millets are good source of fibers (soluble-insoluble). Some popular types of millets include pearl millet, foxtail millet, finger millet, and sorghum.

India is the top most producers of millets followed by Nigeria for the year 2000 and 2009. In India, eight millets species (Sorghum, Pearl millet, Finger millet, Foxtail millet, Kodo millet, Proso millet, Barnyard millet and Little millet) are commonly cultivated under rain fed conditions.

Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) is a warm season crop, intolerant of low temperatures but fairly resistant to serious pests and diseases. Its remarkable ability to thrive in diverse climatic conditions and various soil types solidifies its position as a vital staple food for millions of people worldwide [1]. Sorghum, when compared to other cereals, offers similar nutritional value in terms of its composition, including protein, fat, carbohydrates, and non-starch polysaccharides. Furthermore, non-nutrient compounds like carotenoids and polyphenols contribute to the grain's numerous health benefits, including anti-oxidative, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer effects. Sorghum also exhibits free radical scavenging properties and boasts high antioxidant activity [2].

Finger millet is nutrient-rich, and the nutritional value can be increased through processing. Vital nutrients like carbohydrates, dietary fiber, essential amino acids, and minerals are present in sufficient amounts in finger millet. The grains are a good option for those with celiac disease because they are free of gluten and are simple to digest [3].

Foxtail millet, like most millets, is also a good source of crude fiber, helps in the digestive process and helps to induce bowel movement, thus producing a laxative effect that is beneficial for a healthy digestive system [4]. All these nutritional properties have made foxtail millet an important ingredient for preparing noodles, nourishing gruel or soup, brewing alcoholic beverages, cereal porridges and pancakes in China [5].

The decline in the cultivation of diverse millet species/varieties despite their rich diversity and adaptability can be attributed to several factors such as the lack of awareness of nutritional benefits, inconveniences in food preparations, lack of processing technologies and a lack of institutional support compared to crops like rice and wheat. This lack of support leads to a shrinking of the millet-growing region. However, despite these challenges, many communities in dry and rain-fed regions still recognize the nutritional and cultural importance of millets. Phenolic compounds found in millets encompass a diverse range of chemical substances such as phenolic acids, flavonoids, and condensed tannins. These compounds are known for their antioxidant properties and have been linked to various health benefits, including reducing the risk of chronic diseases such as cardiovascular diseases, cancer, and diabetes. Millets, is a good source of crude fiber, helps in the digestive process and helps to induce bowel movement, thus producing a laxative effect that is beneficial for a healthy digestive system. Incorporating millets into the diet can provide a rich source of these beneficial compounds, offering both nutritional and health advantages. The present study was undertaken to analyze the nutrient composition, fibre content and antioxidant potential of local varieties of different millets. The research also explored the diverse phytochemicals present in these millets.

Fig 1: Different varieties of millets used in the study.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

A. Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

The samples were collected from PDKV Akola and Buldhana, Maharashtra, India and subjected for removal of stones and cleaned for further analysis. Cleaned millet samples were grounded into fine powder and an ethanolic extract was prepared for the phytochemical analysis by using Soxhlet apparatus. Further analysis was carried out using following standard procedures:

1. Test for Carbohydrates: Molisch's test
2. Test for Phenols: Phenol test
3. Test for Tannins: Alkali reagent test
4. Test for Flavonoid: NaOH test
5. Test for Glycosides: Molisch's test

B. Determination Of Percentage Crude Fibre Content

To find out the crude fibre contents in the millets sample, acid and subsequent alkali treatment followed by drying and ashing takes place. Which involve the standard biochemical protocol.

Calculations:

$$\% \text{ crude fiber in ground sample} = \frac{\text{Loss in weight on ignition } (W_2 - W_1) - (W_3 - W_1)}{\text{Weight of the sample } (W_s)} \times 100$$

Where,

pre-weighed crucible (W₁)

Weight of crucible with dried residue (W₂)

Weight of crucible with ashed residue (W₃)

C. Determination Of Carbohydrates Concentration

Determination of carbohydrates contents was carried out by the standard procedure of Anthrone reagent. Absorbance of standard was measured using the UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 630nm. Standard graph was drawn by plotting the concentration on x-axis verses absorbance on y-axis. Using standard graph and formulae, the concentration of carbohydrates in millet samples was determined. D-glucose used as a standard having concentration 10(μg/ml).

Calculations:

$$\text{Amount of carbohydrate present in 100mg of the sample} = \frac{\text{mg of glucose}}{\text{Volume of test sample}} \times 100$$

D. Determination Of Percent Crude Fat Content

The dried sample was placed in a porous thimble. The Soxhlet apparatus was assembled. The flask was filled with petroleum ether and heated until the solvent reached its boiling point. As the solvent vapor rose, it condensed and dripped into the sample chamber. The solvent permeated the sample, dissolving the fat. The condensed solvent then drained back into the flask. This extraction process was repeated multiple times, typically over 4 hours.

For fat recovery and analysis, the solvent containing the dissolved fat was collected from the flask in the beaker (pre weight beaker, W₁). The solvent was evaporated to recover the fat. The fat residue with beaker was weighed(W₂), and the percentage crude fat content was calculated by the following formula.

Calculations:

$$\text{Percentage of crude fat of the given sample} = \frac{W2 - W1}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

E. Determination Of Protein Concentration

The protein contents was determined according to Lowry method [6]. Results were referred to the standard curve of BSA (Bovin Serum Albumin) having concentration of 500 (µg/ml).

F. Total Phenolic Contents

The total phenolic content of millets was determined spectrophotometrically using Folin-Ciocalteu’s reagent. The extract (100 µl ;1 mg/ml) was mixed with 100 µl of Folin-Ciocalteu’s phenol reagent and kept for 5 min. A volume of 1.00 ml of a 7% Na₂CO₃ solution was added to the reaction mixture followed by addition of 1.30 ml of deionized (DI) water. The mixture was kept in the dark at ambient temperature for 90 min and thereafter the absorbance measured at 750 nm. A calibration graph was prepared using Gallic acid as the standard and the total phenolic content in the extract was expressed as milligrams of Gallic acid equivalents in one gram of extract [7].

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The result obtained from phytochemical screening of each variety of millets is tabulated as follows in table 1

TABLE 1
PRESENCE AND ABSENCE OF PHYTOCHEMICALS

Sr. No.	Test	Sorghum millet				Finger millet				Foxtail millet	Little millet	
		PKV Kalyani	PKV Kranti	CSV 34	CSV 45	Phule Nachani	Phule Kasari	BFM-19-E-1	Dapoli-3	PDKV Yashshree	Phule Eakadashi	BLM-18-21
1	Carbohydrates	+	+	+	+	++	++	+	+++	++	++	+
2	Phenols	+	+	++	++	+++	+++	++	+++	++	+	++
3	Tannins	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	++	+	++
4	Flavonoid	+	+	++	++	-	-	-	-	+	++	+
5	Glycoside	+	+	+	+	++	++	+	++	++	+	++

(+) = Presence Of Phytoconstituents

(-) = Absence of Phytoconstituents

CSV 45 and CSV 34 showed higher contents of carbohydrates than the other varieties of Sorghum millet.

P. Nachani and P. Kasari showed higher contents of phenol than the other varieties of Finger millet. Foxtail and little millet showed mixed results of presence of phytoconstituents. Flavonoids are abundant phenolic group present in Sorghum, Foxtail and little millet varieties and Phenols are abundant in Finger millet varieties.

TABLE 2
DETAILED OVERVIEW OF CRUDE FIBRE CONTENT AND NUTRITIONAL COMPOSITION PRESENT IN THE MILLET SAMPLES:

Tests	Sorghum Millet				Finger millet				Foxtail millet	Little millet	
	PKV Kalyani	PKV Kranti	CSV 34	CSV 45	Phule Nachani	Phule Kasari	BFM-19-E-1	Dapoli-3	PDKV Yashshree	Phule Eakadashi	BLM-18-21
Crude fibre (%)	12.6	7.9	12.5	4.1	4.4	7.5	6.4	4.9	5	5.2	5.9
Carbohydrates (µg/ml)	15.3	16.8	18.6	17.8	16.5	20	17.25	25.5	16.2	17.75	19.2
Proteins (µg/ml)	283.3	366.6	400	341.6	300	200	308.3	208.3	325	283.3	241.6
Crude Fat (%)	4.3	3.9	4.6	3.8	8.2	7.6	6.3	3.2	4.5	5.9	5.5

A. Crude Fiber Content

Crude fibre content was high in PKV Kalyani 12.6% variety of sorghum Similarly P. Kasari 7.5% variety of finger millet was high in fibre content. PDKV Yashshree, the variety of foxtail millet was found to be 5% and the BLM-18-21, variety of little millet was found to be 5.9%.

The crude fibre contents are varied from 4.1% to 12.6% percent with varying varieties of millets. Those results are near to those found by Joshi and Katoch (1990), Kamath and Belavady (1980) who reported that the crude fibre contents in finger millet 3.6%, 3.7% and 3.6% [8].

Fig: Millet residue before ashing.

Fig: Millet residue after ashing.

B. Protein Contents

The crude protein content among sorghum varieties, CSV 34 exhibited the highest protein content at 400 (µg/ml). In finger millet varieties, BFM-19-E-1 had the highest protein content at 308.3 (µg/ml). Among foxtail millet varieties, PDKV Yashshree contained 325 (µg/ml) of protein. Phule Eakadashi had a protein content of 283.3 (µg/ml), followed by BLM-18-21 at 241.66 (µg/ml) among little millet varieties.

Fig.: Standard tubes of Proteins.

C. Carbohydrate Contents

Among sorghum varieties, CSV34 exhibited the highest carbohydrate content at 18.62µg/ml. For finger millet varieties, Dapoli-3 had the highest carbohydrate concentration at 25.50µg/ml. Foxtail millet variety PDKV Yashshree registered 16.25µg/ml, while little millet variety BLM-18-21 recorded 19.5µg/ml, followed by Phule Eakadashi at 17.75µg/ml.

Fig.: Standard tubes of Carbohydrates.

D. Crude Fats Content

It was observed that Finger and Little millet exhibited higher crude fat contents compared to sorghum and foxtail millet. Among the sorghum varieties, CSV 34 displayed the highest crude fat content at 4.6%. Similarly, in finger millet, Phule Nachani had the highest crude fat content at 8.2%. Foxtail millet variety PDKV Yashshree exhibited 4.5% crude fat content. Little millet variety, Phule Eakadashi showed the highest content at 5.9%, followed by BLM-18-21 at 5.5%.

The results obtained were in between the results of the Zhang, A., Liu (et al., 2015) which were ranged from 3.38% to 6.49%, and the average was 4.51% [9].

E. The Total Phenolic Content

TPC is quantified in terms of Gallic acid equivalents per milliliter ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) of extract. Among the different millet varieties, little millets exhibited the highest total phenolic content, followed by sorghum, Finger, and Foxtail millet varieties. Specifically, Phule Eakadashi, a variety of little millet, demonstrated $235 \mu\text{g/ml}$ of TPC, with BLM-18-21 following closely at $195 \mu\text{g/ml}$. In the sorghum millet category, CSV 34 displayed the highest TPC content at $195 \mu\text{g/ml}$, trailed by CSV 45 at $180 \mu\text{g/ml}$, PKV Kranti at $165 \mu\text{g/ml}$, and PKV Kalyani at $140 \mu\text{g/ml}$. Among Finger millet varieties, Dapoli-3 exhibited the highest TPC content at $190 \mu\text{g/ml}$, followed by Phule Kasari at $175 \mu\text{g/ml}$, Phule Nachani at $155 \mu\text{g/ml}$, and BFM-19-E-1 at $145 \mu\text{g/ml}$. PDKV Yashshree, a type of Foxtail millet, displayed the lowest phenolic activity at $130 \mu\text{g/ml}$.

Fig.: Concentration vs Absorbance graph of Standard total phenols.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The study showed that the different varieties of same millets contain variations in crude fibre. It was found that the high fibre content in millets due to its incomplete or slow fermentation by microflora in the colon can promote normal laxation which prevents constipation. High fibre content in daily diet can thus reduce the risk of celiac diseases.

The study threw light on presence of secondary metabolites such as glycosides, phenols, flavonoids, tannins in different varieties of sorghum, finger, Foxtail and Little millets. The study can conclude that millets are good for the dietary management of cardiovascular diseases and oxidative stress due to the presence of flavonoid and phenolic compounds.

The study emphasized on the nutritional composition and health benefits of locally available millets in Vidarbha region. Millets are staple food source that is not only providing major nutrients like protein, carbohydrate, fat etc. but also provide ample of vitamins and minerals. Our study explored the presence of phytochemicals with high antioxidant activity in BLM-18-21 variety of little millet. The study also impacted on developing specific agenda for these crops which must be recognized as an important food to introduce the millets as a nutritious food, fulfil the nutritional need of global population and to find ways to consume the millets nutritionally, effectively and to reduce the problems of malnutrition and other health problems like obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, skin problems, cancer, celiac disease etc.

This study highlighted millets as “food medicine” embracing millets as a regular part of our diet that can lead to enhanced overall well-being and a healthier lifestyle. With their versatility and numerous health advantages, millets undoubtedly deserve a prominent place in our daily food choices.

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